

REGIONAL COMMUNITIES & CASE STUDIES

www.soildiveragro.eu

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PREFACE

Innovative management practices and cropping systems with potential positive effects on European agriculture via farm productivity, soil biodiversity and environmental quality will be analyzed and/or tested in SoildiverAgro project. With this aim, 15 field case studies were established in real commercial farms and experimental plots provided by SoildiverAgro beneficiaries.

Field case studies are based mainly on wheat and potato, two crops widely cultivated in Europe across the different European pedoclimatic areas. They can be found in almost all European countries covering large areas of arable land. Wheat is the most important crop among cereals in terms of surface and production, whereas potato is the most important among root crops. Vegetables will be also considered in diversified-cropping systems. SoildiverAgro is testing innovative management practices and cropping systems based on mycorrhiza and plant growth promoting bacteria, appropriate management of soil organisms, suitable crop rotations and intercropping, pest alert systems, nutrient catch crops, trap crops for pest control, by-products as soil ameliorants and adequate tillage systems. All these management practices and cropping systems aim for: 1) enhancement of soil biodiversity; 2) reduction of pest/diseases incidence; 3) increases in plant growth and development; 4) increases in crop yields, quality and value; 5) the reduction of inputs (fertilizers, pesticides, water, fuel); 6) increases in soil fertility; 7) reductions of soil and water contamination; 8) reduction in GHG emissions; and 9) increase in soil C sequestration. Case studies were setup in farms from 6 pedoclimatic regions: Mediterranean South (MDS), Lusitanian (LUS), Atlantic Central (ATC), Atlantic North (ATN), Nemoral (NEM) and Boreal (BOR). These regions still cover all the main climatic regions in Europe (Mediterranean, Atlantic, Continental and Boreal), as well as a large edaphic variability.

David Fernández Calviño
Project Coordinator

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Multi-actor approach (MAA)

SoildiverAgro is a multi-actor project which follows a methodology based on the relationships between 3 different groups, organized and composed by several actors to involve multipliers from all the whole value chain:

- **SoildiverAgro partners.**

SoildiverAgro consortium involves 22 partners from 7 EU countries.

- **External Advisory Board.**

The main function of the External Advisory Board (EAB) is the evaluation of the project progress, and providing guidance regarding future work.

- **SoildiverAgro Community.**

Farmers will be engaged by region (Mediterranean, Lusitanian, Atlantic, Continental, Nemoral, Boreal).

This strategy is addressed to ensure an effective involvement of Stakeholders throughout the SoildiverAgro life span and beyond.

Objectives:

- To improve knowledge exchange between scientists, and stakeholders.
- To co-create new knowledge.
- To put into practice research results.
- To boost interactive and demand-driven innovation.
- To focus on real problems or opportunities.
- To allow partners with complementary types of knowledge join forces in the project activities from the beginning to the end.

In order to reach these objectives, the project Work plan includes several activities directly involving a relevant number of stakeholders (surveys, discussion groups, consultation/demonstration workshops, field days, etc.) based on the involvement level needed.

INFORM

LISTEN

CONSULT

INVOLVE

COLLABORATE

→ *Involvement level*

Methodology

This methodology is conceived as a matrix organizational structure with two main dimensions:

- **Geographical dimension.**

This structure is conceived considering the “Regional Coordinator” (RC) as a facilitator (following the Innovation Brokering concept to contact the end-users and involve different stakeholders covering the whole value chain at local/regional level (policy makers, industry, consumers, etc.). Working with “umbrella” organizations such as cooperatives, associations, etc. will be key to reach a relevant number of stakeholders.

- **Technical dimension.**

This structure is composed of “WP leaders (WPL)” that will need to interact with the stakeholders (through the regional communities) to collect information, validate information, disseminate results or simply communicate about the project activities. WP Leaders will have a scientific responsible role charge of preparing the technical contents to be exchanged with stakeholders.

“Stakeholder is any identifiable groups or individual who can affect or is affected by organisational performance in terms of its products, policies an work process”

↳ R. E. Freeman, 1984

→ MAA methodology work flow

Practice Abstracts

SoildiverAgro: Empowering Farmers with Practical, Science-Based Agricultural Solutions

SoildiverAgro is committed to supporting farmers in the transition toward more sustainable and resilient agricultural systems. As part of this initiative, the project is developing a comprehensive set of **Practice Abstracts**, designed to translate cutting-edge scientific research into practical, easy-to-implement strategies for improving soil health, enhancing biodiversity, and optimizing crop management.

These concise yet informative guides cover a wide range of essential topics, offering farmers actionable insights into **enhancing soil biodiversity, managing pesticide use, and adopting sustainable farming practices** that promote long-term soil fertility and ecosystem stability. Each abstract distills complex research findings into clear, step-by-step recommendations, enabling farmers to apply the latest innovations directly to their fields with confidence and ease. By bridging the gap between research and real-world agricultural challenges, SoildiverAgro ensures that valuable, science-backed knowledge reaches those who need it most. Through these practical resources, farmers gain the tools and expertise necessary to **increase productivity while preserving environmental health**, ultimately fostering a more sustainable and resilient agricultural landscape for future generations.

www.soildiveragro.eu/publications/practice-abstracts/

Decision Support Tool

The **Decision Support Tool (DST)** is a free, web-based software developed through the SoildiverAgro project to help end-users, including farmers and other stakeholders, optimize their wheat cropping systems and management practices.

The DST uses machine learning models developed from experimental data collected during the SoildiverAgro project to predict agricultural soil properties. It takes into account environmental, physicochemical, and land-use parameters, as well as biodiversity indices. The tool guides users through a step-by-step process, asking for key information such as pedoclimatic conditions, crop location, agricultural challenges, and current cropping systems. Based on this input, the DST provides tailored recommendations to enhance productivity, profitability, and sustainability.

Easily accessible through the SoildiverAgro website, the DST provides valuable insights that help stakeholders make more informed decisions and optimize their farming practices.

www.soildiveragro.eu/publications/decision-support-tool/

White Paper on Policy Recommendations

The SoildiverAgro White Paper brings together research findings and stakeholder input to offer clear policy recommendations for improving soil biodiversity in European agriculture. It aligns proposed strategies with existing EU and regional policies, identifies knowledge gaps, and sets practical indicators to support on-farm implementation. Developed through collaboration with farmers, experts, and policymakers, the White Paper ensures that future policies are both effective and grounded in real-world needs.

Best Management Practices

This manual compiles the best agricultural practices identified from case studies across Europe during the SoildiverAgro project. Focused on boosting soil biodiversity, it offers practical, innovative solutions that improve soil health, reduce inputs like fertilizers and pesticides, and enhance sustainability on farms. Developed with input from farmers, researchers, and policymakers, the guidelines support both environmental and economic benefits—helping address real agricultural challenges while promoting soil fertility, reducing emissions, and improving resource efficiency.

Map of case studies

CS 15 PETLA		Nutrient catch crops
CS 14 A/B MTJ/TT		Till systems
★ CS 13 PETLA		By-products
★ CS 12 EULS		Till system Pest alert systems Suitable crop diversification
★ CS 11 FAR		Organisms interaction management
CS 10 B FAR		Organisms interaction management
CS 10 A FAR		Organisms interaction management
CS 9 POMONA		By-products
★ CS 8 PSKW		Till systems By-products
CS 7 INAGRO		Suitable crop diversification
CS 6 ILVO		By-products Suitable crop diversification
CS 5 UVIGO		Pest alert system
CS 4 UVIGO		Mycorrhiza
★ CS 3 UVIGO		Suitable crop diversification Trap crops for pest control
CS 2 UPCT		By-products Suitable crop diversification Plant growth promoting microorganisms
★ CS 1 UPCT		Suitable crop diversification Plant growth promoting microorganisms

CROPS TYPE

Potatoes

Wheat

Vegetables

Best Management Practices

MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER

UPCT, (Spain)

COORDINATION

Raúl Zornoza

PhD in Environmental Sciences. Expert in soil quality and degradation, soil microbial diversity, organic matter dynamics and sustainable soil management practices.

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Objective

The vegetables and cereals cultivation in the Mediterranean region are mainly threatened by low availability of nutrients due to $\text{pH} > 7.5$, with the need to continuously add fertilizers. Most of the nutrients added precipitate in soil fast owing to the high pH, remaining unavailable for the crops. In addition, the high use of pesticides and monocultures are increasing pest/disease resistances, with more dependence to use more products, that may have negative effects on soil organisms. The climate conditions of the area favour soil organic matter degradation, which linked to monocultures and intensive tillage leads to soil degradation. In general, farmers are concerned about the difficulties in maintaining high crop yields due to soil nutrient depletion, pests and diseases. However, there is still lack of information about how the management of soil biodiversity can enhance the resilience of their farms and increase availability of nutrients and resistance to pests/diseases while decreasing the use of external inputs but maintaining the same yields.

There are two ways to tackle these problems: proper management of biodiversity by nature-based solutions and technology, which may evolve in parallel. With SoildiverAgro we aim to make a proper use of biodiversity by use biotechnological products based on microorganisms to increase soil nutrient availability, decrease the incidence of soil-borne diseases, increase soil organic matter and water retention, by decrease of chemical inputs. This will be associated with proper selection of crop diversification to enhance the functionality of soil macro and microorganisms, responsible for enhancing soil health, and so productivity. This is one of the challenges in the Mediterranean agriculture, and the results of this project, properly transferred to farmers, policy-makers and land managers may contribute to increase farm sustainability with the decrease of external inputs, by increasing soil biodiversity.

Stakeholders consultations

DISCUSSION GROUP

📅 15.09.2020 | Cartagena, Spain (Online).

Share the main agronomic problems identified by surveys on **potato production**.

8 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness.

📅 16.09.2020 | Cartagena, Spain (Online).

Share the main agronomic problems identified by surveys on **wheat production**.

16 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness.

Proyecto SoildiverAgro
GRUPO DE DEBATE
Prácticas sostenibles de manejo agrícola en el cultivo de la patata

Intercambio de experiencias y opiniones entre agricultores, investigadores, técnicos especialistas, personal experto en la administración pública, proveedores, etc.

Martes 15 de septiembre de 2020 a las 18:00h.
Reunión virtual a través de la plataforma Teams

www.soildiveragro.eu

Proyecto SoildiverAgro
GRUPO DE DEBATE
Prácticas sostenibles de manejo agrícola en el cultivo del trigo

Intercambio de experiencias y opiniones entre agricultores, investigadores, técnicos especialistas, personal experto en la administración pública, proveedores, etc.

Miércoles 16 de septiembre de 2020 a las 18:00h.
Reunión virtual a través de la plataforma Teams

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REGIONAL MEETING

📅 29.09.2020 | Cartagena, Spain (Online).

Solutions for wheat and vegetables cultivation by the management of **soil biodiversity**, searching to find the relationship between soil biological groups, crop production and quality.

19 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness.

📅 22.06.2022 | Caravaca de la Cruz, Spain.

Regional meeting and field day.

45 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users and scientific community.

📅 26.06.2022 | Cartagena, Spain.

Workshop on both CS2 in the cereal fields and CS1 in the vegetable experimentation farm of Murcia.

30 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users.

📅 09.10.2023 | Cartagena, Spain.

Regional meeting.

28 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users.

📅 10.02.2025 | Cartagena, Spain.

Mediterranean region final meeting.

48 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, stakeholders, and team members.

Stakeholders consultations

FIELD DAYS

📅 22.06.2022 | Caravaca de la Cruz, Spain.

Field Day and Regional workshop in CS1.

28 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, technicians, agronomists, advisors, researchers.

📅 24.06.2022 | Cartagena, Spain.

Workshop on both CS2 in the cereal fields and CS1 in the vegetable experimentation farm of Murcia.

30 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, technicians, agronomists, advisors, environmentalists, consumers.

📅 03.11.2023 | Cartagena, Spain.

Field days.

40 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users.

TRAINING DAYS

📅 09.02.2024 | Cartagena, Spain.

Training course.

PARTICIPANTS: Students.

OTHERS

📅 25-26.02.2025 | Cartagena, Spain.

Spanish National Conference on Organic Agriculture.

PARTICIPANTS: Researchers, agricultural professionals, government agencies, organic businesses, and technology experts.

CASE STUDY 1

Use of soil biodiversity to reduce soil-borne diseases/pests incidence and increase nutrient availability in potatoes cropped in multiple cropping and rotations

Best Management Practices

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this case study is to increase soil nutrient availability and soil water retention capacity and reduce soil-borne diseases/pests incidence to decrease productions costs.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

We will check better optimal multiple cropping and rotations to enhance soil fertility and biodiversity and reduce soil-borne diseases/pests incidence, integrated pest control and addition of nutrient solubilizing biological agents (plant growth promoting bacteria (PGPB) and fungi).

STATE OF THE ART

The potatoes and vegetables cultivation in the area is highly intense in external inputs to increase fertility (inorganic fertilizers and manure), reduce the incidence of diseases/pests (pesticides) and increase yields (irrigation water). Multiple cropping and rotations are common, but not optimized to maximize the development of soil organisms.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Finding adequate crop rotations/multiple cropping to manage soil biodiversity, not performed so far. Assessment of PGPB and fungi on soil biodiversity, since it has been proved their efficiency to enhance yields, but little is known about their effect on native microbial communities and time evolution. Maybe plant combination and organic matter addition could enhance native soil biodiversity with no need for bioaugmentation.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

The vegetables cultivation in the area are mainly threatened by low availability of nutrients due to pH > 8, with the need to continuously add external inputs, the excessive use of water and the presence of cyst nematodes. This makes productions costs be high.

CROPS

LOCATION

Cartagena (Spain)

PARTNERS

UPCT

ASAJA

FYNECO

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Crop rotation & Addition of nutrient solubilizing biological agents (plant growth promoting bacteria (PGPB) and fungi)

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

13 farmers

→ Case Study 1 Infographic (UPTC)

CASE STUDY 2

Use of soil biodiversity to increase nutrient and water availability and reduce soil-borne diseases incidence to increase wheat yields

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this case study is to increase nutrient and water availability and reduce soil-borne diseases incidence to increase wheat yields.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

We will introduce multiple cropping and rotations to enhance soil fertility and biodiversity and reduce soil-borne diseases/pests incidence, add green manure to improve soil structure and soil water holding capacity and addition of nutrient solubilizing biological agents (plant growth promoting bacteria (PGPB) and fungi).

STATE OF THE ART

The wheat cultivation in the area is highly intense in machinery and pesticides use, with low or nil fertilization and absence of rotations, with use of fallow periods to avoid soil exhaustion by cropping.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Finding adequate crop rotations/multiple cropping to manage soil biodiversity, not performed so far with this aim. Assessment of PGPB and fungi on soil biodiversity, since it has been proved their efficiency to enhance yields, but little is known about their effect on native microbial communities and time evolution. Maybe plant combination and organic matter addition could enhance native soil biodiversity with no need for bioaugmentation.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

The wheat cultivation in the area are mainly threatened by low availability of nutrients due to $\text{pH} > 8$ and low water content owing to climatic constraints, with affection of fungi after rainfall events. This makes crop yields be low.

CROPS

LOCATION

Caravaca (Spain)

PARTNERS

UPCT

ASAJA

FYNECO

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Addition of nutrient solubilizing biological agents (plant growth promoting bacteria (PGPB) and fungi) & crop rotation

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

10 farmers

→ Case Study 2 Infographic (UPTC)

LUSITANEAN

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER

UVIGO, (Spain)

COORDINATION

Paula Pérez Rodríguez

Agricultural engineer and PhD in Soil Science. Postdoctoral researcher in Plant and Soil Science Department at the University of Vigo. Research experience in soil heavy metals pollution, heavy metals immobilization by bio-adsorbents, nutrients and pollutants interaction in plant-rhizosphere-soil system, degradation mechanisms and nutrient sources by stable isotopes.

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Objective

Potato and cereals are the most extensive crops cultivated in the Lusitanian region. However, climatological and soil conditions are unfavourable for their sustainable development. Potato crops are threatened by a high incidence of cyst nematode, common scab, and fungal attacks, while cereal crops are also highly attacked by fungi. All these diseases necessitate the application of large amounts of agrochemicals to control them. For instance, nematicides, fungicides and fertilizers are widely applied in the area. To control the common scab, potato cultivation is performed at $\text{pH} < 5$, which makes P availability very low despite the high levels of P in the soil. To solve this, P-fertilizers are added to the soil. In addition, the absence of proper crop rotations leads to the need for N-fertilizers in order to avoid nutrient deficiency in crops. All these issues result in the area being highly polluted due to the application of large amounts of inputs, both pesticides and fertilizers, contributing to water pollution and a decline in soil biodiversity. Moreover, farmers are concerned about the profitability of crops, due to low potato values because of their poor appearance, and the high costs of inputs.

In SoildiverAgro, we aim to apply different management practices, pest alert systems and biotechnological products based on microorganisms to address these issues by reducing pest diseases, increasing nutrient availability to get a reduction of agricultural inputs, and enhancing soil biodiversity. All these challenges will be tested in SoildiverAgro in cooperation with local farmers, and the results could make agriculture in the Lusitanian region more sustainable, profitable and environmental-friendly.

Stakeholders consultations

DISCUSSION GROUP

📅 11.03.2020 | Xinzo de Limia, Spain.

Implementation of potential more sustainable agricultural management practices.

39 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness people, policymakers, industry advisors.

📅 14.12.2022 | Xinzo de Limia, Spain.

Workshop.

40 PARTICIPANTS.

📅 14.03.2024 | Galiza, Spain.

Workshop.

43 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researches, agribusiness, policy makers.

REGIONAL MEETING

📅 18.11.2020 | Galiza, Spain (Online).

Presentation of SoildiverAgro project, current status of SoildiverAgro and presentation of Lusitanean case studies and discussion.

22 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness, policymakers, industry advisors.

📅 14.12.2024 | Galiza, Spain.

Regional meeting.

37 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users.

FIELD DAYS

📅 30.04.2025 | Galiza, Spain.

Visit to SdA CS3 experiments.

16 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers and stakeholders.

📅 13.05.2025 | Galiza, Spain.

Field Visit to SdA CS3 experimental plots.

28 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers and stakeholders.

📅 14.05.2025 | Galiza, Spain.

Field Visit to vineyards sampled in BIOservicES project.

28 PARTICIPANTS: Project's partners.

📅 28.05.2025 | Galiza, Spain.
Visit to SdA CS4 and CS5 experiments.
29 PARTICIPANTS: End-users.

TRAINING DAYS

📅 26-27.04.2024 | Galiza, Spain.
Training to Students in O Caurel.
20 PARTICIPANTS: Students.

📅 23.05.2025 | Galiza, Spain.
Training to university teachers and PhD students.
21 PARTICIPANTS: Teachers and PhD students.

📅 28.05.2025 | Galiza, Spain.
Training to end-users.
33 PARTICIPANTS: End-users.

OTHERS

📅 05.12.2024 | Santiago de Compostela, Spain.
Suelos Vivos event.
54 PARTICIPANTS: Researchers, experts.

CASE STUDY 3

Use of crop diversification and trap crops in potato fields to reduce the incidence of cyst nematode, decrease the use of nematicides, increase the crop yields and increase the soil biodiversity

Best Management Practices

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this case study is to reduce the incidence of cyst nematodes in potatoes crops, reduce the use of nematicides and increase the crops yields and soil biodiversity.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

We will introduce suitable crop rotations to increase the soil biodiversity and, together with and adequate management of trap crops, reduce the incidence of cyst nematodes for potatoes production.

STATE OF THE ART

The potatoes cultivation in the area is highly intense in nematicides use and it lacks appropriate rotations. Also the use of trap crops (*Solanum sisymbriifolium*) for pest control is very low developed and many complications must be solved before trap crops use, specially the adequate conditions for the trap crops germination.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

By finding adequate crop rotations and a suitable trap crop management, soil biodiversity will be increased due to the existence of higher plant diversity and a reduction in pesticide use. The incidence of cyst nematodes will be reduced without the employment of nematicides, decreasing farm costs and increasing crop yields. The potential damage caused by nematicides on soil biodiversity will disappear, together with a reduction in soil and water pollution. Moreover, the introduction of legumes in the crop rotation will contribute to a decrease in N fertilization, and trap crops burial will contribute to increasing the C storage in soils.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

The potatoes cultivation in the area is mainly threatened by the high incidence of cyst nematode, which, leads to important yield decreases, and hence, the high use of nematicides to try to save crops. This high use of nematicides by farmers can be an important cost for potatoes production, contributing to soil and surrounding water pollution and also to a decrease in soil biodiversity.

CROPS

LOCATION

Sandiás (Spain)

PARTNERS

UVIGO

INORDE

RRG

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Crop diversification and trap crop

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

13 farmers

→ Case Study 3 Infographic (UVIGO)

CASE STUDY 4

Use of mycorrhiza in potato fields to reduce the incidence of common scab, decrease the use of phosphorus fertilizers, increase the crop yields and increase the soil biodiversity

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this case study is to reduce the common scab incidence in potatoes crops, decrease P fertilization, allow potatoes cultivation at higher pH, and hence increase crops yields and soil biodiversity.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

We will introduce mycorrhiza associated with potatoes crop to protect plants against common scab and increase P uptake by plants. Additionally we will perform soil sampling and establish trap crops to isolate the native AMF species from the target field sites.

STATE OF THE ART

The use of mycorrhiza associated with potatoes cultivation in the area was negligible, and research on native mycorrhiza for use in potatoes production to increase yields and protection against diseases has not been performed yet.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

An adequate potatoes colonization by mycorrhiza will protect crops against common scab, provide better P nutrition, and allow cultivation at higher soil pH. Therefore, production and value will increase, P inputs will decrease, and soil biodiversity will increase.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

Potatoes cultivation must be performed in very acidic conditions (pH <5.0) to avoid common scab disease due to the high organic matter contents in the soils. Under these conditions, P availability is very low, and despite the presence of high amounts of phosphorus in the soils, farmers in the area use large amounts of P fertilizers annually. Additionally, in very acid soils, the diversity of microorganisms and soil fauna is generally low. Common scab causes poor appearance in potatoes, and hence, they can be only used for industrial uses, not for direct commercialization, decreasing the potatoes value.

CROPS

LOCATION

Xinzo da Limia (Spain)

PARTNERS

UVIGO

INORDE

RRG

SYMBIOM

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Use of mycorrhiza

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

13 farmers

→ Case Study 4 Infographic (UVIGO)

CASE STUDY 5

Implementation of the Decision Support Systems (pest alert system) to reduce the use of fungicides in potato and wheat crops and their impact in biodiversity

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this case study is to reduce the use of these fungicide treatments, improving the forecast of the risk of the disease.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

The proposal will consider phenology, aerobiological data and meteorology to obtain the best decision support systems for the management of some potato and cereal fungal diseases.

STATE OF THE ART

The use of fungicides is often based on a schedule calendar, which marks the onset of the first application and the frequency of the consecutive ones, applied independently of the risk of infection. This system allows farmers to have inadequate control of the disease with great weaknesses. Primarily, the economic cost of acquiring and applying these treatments and the negative and costly environmental footprint in water, soil, and air and as a consequence in biodiversity.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

An efficient forecast of the risk of infection by a pathogen in a crop is indispensable for a sustainable use of the agricultural systems. This helps farms to save production costs, decrease fungicides and fuel consumption, reduce soil and surrounding water pollution and increase soil biodiversity.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

The environmental conditions of this region favor the attack of fungi on potatoes and cereal crops. The control of these plant diseases is based mainly on the application of high amounts of preventive fungicide treatments. The high amounts of fungicide treatments require an important number of machinery passes on field, contributing to soil compaction and together with fungicides, lead to decreases in soil biodiversity.

CROPS

LOCATION

Sandiás (Spain)

PARTNERS

UVIGO

INORDE

RRG

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Pest Alert System

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

13 farmers

→ Case Study 5 Infographic (UVIGO)

ATLANTIC CENTRAL

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER

EV-ILVO, (Belgium)

COORDINATION

Lieven Waeyenberge

Senior researcher at ILVO, with expertise in molecular diagnostics of plant-parasitic and entomopathogenic nematodes. In this regard, he cooperated with several international research groups to aid in resolving diagnostic problems. Since a couple of years, his focus shifted towards amplicon-sequencing (a Next Generation Sequencing technique) to characterize soil nematode communities. Nematode communities are considered as capable bio-indicators of ecosystem health.

Lieven.waeyenberge@ilvo.vlaanderen.be

Objective

A questionnaire and regional discussion group meetings with stakeholders and end-users revealed and prioritised the main threats affecting the agro-ecosystems of the Atlantic Central region and the qualitative assessment of their severity. Use of chemical fertilizers and liquid manure or slurry still cause a too large leakage of nitrate and phosphate in surface water and groundwater, intensive management regimes cause a deficit of soil organic matter, and a general drop of 'soil health', recognized by degraded biological and structural conditions, causes additional problems like soil erosion and water shortage.

Field experiments have been established to test different management practices for wheat, potatoes and vegetables in order to address the above mentioned agricultural threats. Especially attention is paid to soil fertility, organic matter content and biodiversity in each case-study in a different way: case-study 6 will investigate the combined effect of with and without 'brown' material co-composted farm yard manure and a differential management of the cover crops (incorporation or mowing), case-study 7 will focus on the effect of cover crop mixtures which will diversify further the cropping system (from simple till 12 species mixtures), case-study 8 will compare different agricultural systems (intensive versus extensive, conventional versus organic), and case-study 9 will investigate the use of different organic fertilization sources like farm yard manure, compost and silage (fermented) grass-clover.

The obtained data of the case-studies will contribute to the analysis of the environmental and economic impact on a farm and regional level. This will finally result in the proper selection of the most promising crop diversification methods (including cover crops), organic fertilizers, and farming systems to enhance the functionality of soil macro- and microorganisms, responsible for enhancing soil health, crop productivity and other ecosystem services.

Stakeholders consultations

DISCUSSION GROUP

📅 19.05.2020 | Merelbeke, Belgium (Online).

Conclusions of the extensification of **vegetable production survey** presentation: What are the main problems and best fitting solutions for vegetable cropping in Flanders?

14 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness, policymakers, industry advisors.

📅 30.06.2020 | Merelbeke, Belgium (Online).

General conclusions of the **potato production survey** were presented: What are the main problems and best fitting solutions in Flanders?

15 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness, policymakers, industry advisors.

📅 06.02.2023 | Belgium.

WP3 Discussion Meeting.

8 PARTICIPANTS: Scientific community.

📅 08.03.2023 | Belgium.

WP3 Discussion Meeting.

6 PARTICIPANTS: Scientific community.

REGIONAL MEETING

📅 18.03.2020 | Belgium.

Regional workshop.

5 PARTICIPANTS: Belgian regional partners, ILVO researchers.

📅 08-09 of 2020 & 02 of 2021 | ILVO, PSKW, Inagro, Pomona, Belgium. (Online and 'in person').

Finalising the details concerning the organisation, maintenance and study-objects of the **case-studies in Flanders**.

15 PARTICIPANTS: Belgian regional partners, researchers and experts in mechanisation, fertilization, plant quality assessment, lab technicians, field workers, advisors.

📅 04.06.2021 | Belgium.

Institutional meeting.

50 PARTICIPANTS: ILVO researchers.

📅 09.03.2022 | Belgium.

Regional meeting.

9 PARTICIPANTS: Scientific community.

📅 14.06.2023 | Belgium.

Scientific Board Meeting.

20 PARTICIPANTS: Scientific community.

Stakeholders consultations

FIELD DAYS

📅 12.08.2020 | Antwerpen, Belgium.

Trial visit on their **organic leek trial field**.

7 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers and distribution sector.

📅 22.06.2021 | Belgium.

Trial visit on their **organic leek trial field**.

15 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers and industry.

📅 09.08.2021 | Belgium.

Field days.

9 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, industry, policy makers, researchers.

📅 29.09.2021 | Rumbeke-Beitem, Belgium.

'Biovelddag' including visit of the SdA field trial.

71 PARTICIPANTS: Researchers, agro-technicians, advisors, farmers (conventional and organic), teachers, organic sector, policy makers and the industry.

📅 19.02.2022 | POMONA, Meerdonk, Melsele & Verrebroek, Belgium.

'Grote info- en Rondneustoer', including visiting the SdA field trial.

MORE THAN 100 PARTICIPANTS: Families, farmers, scientist-agronomists, civil society.

📅 22.06.2022 | Belgium.

Field visit growers of Belchim.

15 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users.

📅 11.08.2022 | Belgium.

Field visit organic growers.

16 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users, public administration, policy makers, scientific community.

📅 08.09.2022 | Belgium.

Field Day CS6.

15 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users, Public administration, Civil society, Policy makers, Scientific community.

📅 20.09.2022 | Belgium.

Field visit institut Agro Angers.

15 PARTICIPANTS: Civil society.

📅 06.10.2022 | Belgium.

Field day CS7.

30 PARTICIPANTS: Organic farmers, advisors, agricultural companies.

📅 02.05.2023 | Belgium.

Field visit Sint-Norbertus instituut duffel.

29 PARTICIPANTS: Civil society.

📅 08.05.2023 | Belgium.

Field visit Sint-Norbertus instituut duffel.

21 PARTICIPANTS: Civil society.

📅 12.06.2023 | Belgium.

Field Day CS9.

31 PARTICIPANTS: Policy makers, Scientific community.

📅 12.06.2023 | Belgium.

Field Day CS8.

31 PARTICIPANTS: Policy makers, Scientific community.

📅 13.06.2023 | Belgium.

Field Day CS6.

32 PARTICIPANTS: Scientific community.

📅 13.06.2023 | Belgium.

Field Day CS7.

32 PARTICIPANTS: Scientific community.

📅 21.06.2023 | Belgium.

Field visit Nordiskalkali to trial fields.

23 PARTICIPANTS: Scientific community.

📅 28.06.2023 | Belgium.

Field Day CS7.

70 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users, Public administration, Civil society, Scientific community.

📅 10.08.2023 | Belgium.

Field visit organic growers.

19 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users, Policy makers, Scientific community.

Stakeholders consultations

TRAINING DAYS

📅 27.04.2021 | Belgium.

Training.

18 PARTICIPANTS: Students.

📅 04.12.2024 | Belgium.

Proefstation PSKW.

58 PARTICIPANTS: Regional growers.

📅 10.02.2025 | Belgium.

Final workshop CS6-7.

82 PARTICIPANTS: Researchers, policy makers, industry, organic sector and farmers.

📅 13.02.2025 | Belgium.

Training session on the use of cover crops (chapter about the relation with soil life).

19 PARTICIPANTS: Regional growers.

📅 19.02.2025 | Belgium.

Training session on beneficial organisms in agriculture (chapter about soil life with end results of CS8 and CS7).

23 PARTICIPANTS: Regional growers.

OTHERS

📅 06.10.2019 | Belgium.

Open house, poster presentation.

1200 PARTICIPANTS: Common people.

📅 07.10.2019 | Belgium.

Open house, poster presentation.

500 PARTICIPANTS: Students.

📅 23.06.2021 | Belgium.

Mini-symposium 'organic research' about results of projects (including SdA) dealing with organic farming.

28 PARTICIPANTS: Researchers, policy makers and farmers.

📅 23.11.2021 | Belgium.

Technical committee Organic growers.

15 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users, researchers, media, policy makers, distribution sector, advisors.

📅 15-19.09.2022 | Belgium.

Festilvo.

110 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers and other stakeholders.

📅 5/12/2022 | Belgium.

Soil Health Conference (International Conference).

194 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end-users (farmers, advisors, input suppliers), public administration, policy-makers, scientific community, NGOs, media.

📅 19.12.2022 | Belgium.

Presentation soil management to growers of Klein-Brabant.

9 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users.

📅 12.06.2023 | Belgium.

General Assembly.

33 PARTICIPANTS: Policy makers, Scientific community.

📅 07.11.2023 | Belgium.

Technical committee Organic growers.

14 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users, Public administration, Scientific community, Media.

CASE STUDY 6

Contrasting soil management strategies in an arable crop rotation inclusive of potatoes to improve soil quality while minimizing external input of P

OBJECTIVE

The objective is to explore to what extent innovative strategies, contributing to soil quality and N supplying capacity, might reduce P surpluses compared to the usual soil management.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

N:P and C:P ratios of farm yard manure (FYM) will be modified by co-composting FYM with 'brown' material (e.g., grass clippings from nature reserves). The effect of co-composted FYM, compared to stockpiled FYM,

on crop performance and soil quality will be assessed in a multiyear field trial with repetitive application of both fertilization products. A blank treatment with no base fertilization is included as well. In the same trial, two different management variants will be applied for cover crop mixtures grown in between the main crops in the rotation. The cover crop mixtures will be either used as green manure or harvested as a fodder crop. Differences in treatments regarding both factors will result in differences with regard to C and N input, and therefore possibly in differences with regard to main crop performance and soil quality.

STATE OF THE ART

An increasing amount of easily available P, as a result of a high soil P status (most of the Flemish agricultural and horticultural land) seems to counteract microbial activity in the rhizosphere. In particular, organic growers rely on this microbial activity in the rhizosphere as a plant feeding mechanism. Therefore, soil management strategies should aim at preventing P surpluses by reducing external input of organic matter.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

This case study will illustrate best practices for soil fertility building while minimizing P input or balancing P input by fertilization products with P export by harvested plant parts.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

Soil management strategies for organic cropping systems will be developed aiming at the sustainment of soil quality on one hand and at a balanced P supply on the other hand.

CROPS

LOCATION

Melle, East-Flanders (Belgium)

PARTNERS

ILVO

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Application of co-composted farm yard manure and use of cover crops

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

6 farmers and 6 other stakeholders
(mainly advisors)

→ Case Study 6 Infographic (ILVO)

CASE STUDY 7

Cover crop mixtures: a promotor of soil biodiversity in potato crops?

OBJECTIVE

The objective is to test the potential beneficial impact of different cover crop mixtures in organic agriculture on soil biological diversity in function of the cultivation of potatoes. Whether more species-diverse mixtures can combine more soil benefiting functions like catching nutrients (nitrogen) is also investigated. By including leguminous species, the function of delivering nitrogen to the following main crops is tested. From these trails, farmers will be able to improve the design of their cover crop mixtures.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

Four different cover crop mixtures will be compared for their impact on soil biodiversity, N mineralization and main crop yield. The same mixtures will be sown in the same place for three years. BAU, the business as usual, is a mixture of phacelia and black oat. Secondly, a mixture of phacelia and Egyptian clover is tested. The two other mixtures are species-diverse: a five species mixture containing phacelia, black oat, Egyptian clover, fodder radish and vetch and a 12-species mixture that combines all the previously mentioned species with the addition of species such as pea, lupine and flax.

STATE OF THE ART

Advisors often recommend organic farmers to use species diverse cover crop mixtures to stimulate the soil diversity. However, little is known about the actual impact of the use of such cover crop mixtures on the soil diversity, nor in the short or longer term.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Increased understanding of the impact of different cover crop mixtures on soil biology and related ecosystem services together with increased knowledge to improve the design of cover crop mixtures.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

Organic farmers heavily rely on an active and diverse soil biology to make their system work. The soil biology needs to be able to digest diverse types of organic material to provide sufficient and timely nutrients for the crops. Moreover, soil microorganisms also need to control soilborne diseases ('suppressiveness of the soil'). The use of species diverse cover crop mixtures could contribute to improve the soil biology.

CROPS

LOCATION

Rumbeke-Beitem (Belgium)

PARTNERS

INAGRO

ILVO

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Use of cover crop mixtures

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

3 farmers and 6 other stakeholders
(mainly advisors)

→ Case Study 7 Infographic (INAGRO)

CASE STUDY 8

Extensification of conventional and organic vegetable farming

Best Management Practices

OBJECTIVE

The objective is to test the positive effect of extensive farming on the soil compared to intensive farming, in conventional and organic vegetable cropping. What is the effect on the fertility of the soil and on soil pathogens when reversing to another farming system.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

We will work on a conventional field and an organic field. Each field will be divided in two halves. On one half, we will continue with an intensive cultivation as a reference. On the other half, we will switch to a more extensive system to study the benefits of it. Reduced tillage, use of compost and green manure will be studied in a system approach.

STATE OF THE ART

In Belgium around 45% of the area of vegetable production outdoors are used for intensive farming. The rest is cultivated in crop rotation with arable crops (extensive farming). The growers are mainly focused on the yield of their crops, sometimes at the expense of the soil quality.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

With these studies we hope to demonstrate the long-term positive effects of extensive and organic farming compared to intensive farming. Growers need to be convinced of the positive effects this type of farming can have on their soil and their crops, even when they don't see immediate results in for example the yield. The goal is to persuade them that investing in a healthy soil will eventually result in a better crop.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

The intensive vegetable production in Belgium with intensive tillage, limited crop rotation and unilateral fertilization has a negative effect on soil quality. This could also lead to a favourable environment for pests and diseases and result in a lower yield and quality of the crop.

CROPS

LOCATION

Sint-Katelijne-Waver (Belgium)

PARTNERS

PSKW

ILVO

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Crop rotation, different cultivation techniques, reduced tillage, and use of compost and green manure

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

3 farmers and 6 other stakeholders (mainly advisors)

LEEK

CELERY

CAULIFLOWER

Inverting tillage

INTENSIVE REFERENCE

Low input of organic matter

COMPARE WITH

ADAPTED SYSTEM FOR SOIL BIODIVERSITY

Non-inverting tillage

Higher input of organic matter

Green manure
(Spring: Phacelia and crimson clover) (Autumn: ryegrass)

INCREASE

Soil microorganisms

Soil quality and organic carbon content

Crop yield and quality

→ *Case Study 8 Infographic (PSKW)*

CASE STUDY 9

Testing different sources of green manure in agro-ecological wheat and potato production

OBJECTIVE

Agro-ecological farming relies on ecological processes to support the production system. It is a holistic way of thinking on agronomy, ecology and biology. In this respect, the objective is to test different sources of locally produced organic fertilizer to increase the SOM content, ameliorate the soil's structure and improve plant health and development. Especially farmyard manure, compost and fermented organic waste will be tested.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

We will divide a field with an organic farming system, in combination with agro-forestry, into different parts. Each part will receive another source of green manure. Especially farmyard manure, compost and fermented organic waste (bokashi) which was produced 'on farm' or locally will be tested.

STATE OF THE ART

Organic farming mostly applies composted or non-composted green manure to increase C-content, and improve the soil's structure. However, fermented organic waste has some additional advantages: improved microbial diversity and activity to produce natural antibiotics, essential vitamins and plant growth hormones; the soil's quality improves further and it gets more resilient against pests and diseases.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

With this experiment we hope to demonstrate that different sources of green manure exist as excellent alternatives the conventional way of external inputs of nutrients. Also we want to demonstrate the potential of fermented organic waste on soil structure, SOM content and improved plant health.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

Conventional farming depends on high amounts of external inputs of fertilizer because it negatively disturbs the soil's capacity to produce crops: nutrients get depleted, the SOM (soil organic matter) content decreases and the structure of the soil deteriorates. The proposed field trial wants to demonstrate that a sustainable way of farming is possible in combination with a reduced dependence of external fertilizers.

CROPS

LOCATION

Verrebroek, East-Flanders
(Belgium)

PARTNERS

POMONA

ILVO

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Application of different types
of green manures, cover crops
incorporated after destruction,
reduced tillage

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

2 farmers and 6 other stakeholders
(mainly advisors)

→ Case Study 9 Infographic (POMONA)

CONTINENTAL

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER

Thünen-Institute (TI), (Germany)

COORDINATION

Stefan Schrader

Stefan Schrader is Deputy Head of the Thünen-Institute of Biodiversity in Braunschweig, Germany, and leader of the soil zoology working group. He is Professor for Soil Biology and Soil Ecology at the Technical University of Braunschweig. His research activity focuses on functional diversity of soil fauna and its provision of ecosystem services in agricultural systems.

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Objective

In the Continental region, increasing infestation pressure from soil-borne pathogens, especially from phytopathogenic fungi such as *Fusarium* or *Alternaria*, is increasingly posing challenges to agriculture. This affects both conventional and organic cultivation of cereals, but also of root crops such as potatoes. The main reasons for this development are rising temperatures as a result of global climate change, densely growing stands and tight crop rotations, especially in high-yield regions, and the reduction of soil tillage intensity to avoid soil erosion. Especially in combination with wet weather conditions, these factors favour the survival and spread of fungal diseases, leading to a reduction in yield levels and, through the formation of mycotoxins, also in yield quality. In the long term, negative effects on soil health, for example through leaching of mycotoxins, cannot be ruled out. In order to counteract this increasing infestation pressure and to avoid associated negative effects, high amounts of external inputs, especially fungicides and plant growth regulators, are currently being applied. However, these high application rates of plant protection products are not without risk, as they endanger soil biodiversity and, as a consequence, the resilience of agroecosystems.

Against this background, there is a great demand for alternative methods of controlling fungal pathogens. In this context, natural bottom-up bioregulation provides a promising approach, as fungivorous soil fauna communities represent effective antagonists against fungal pathogens, which can also accelerate the degradation of mycotoxins. With *SoildiverAgro*, we aim to identify management measures in wheat and potato cultivation that promote fungivorous soil fauna communities and ensure optimal use of the ecosystem service "bioregulation". The focus is on the use of undersowing and increasing seed row spacing while reducing pesticides. Thus, the case studies are conducted within commercial farms in close collaboration with farmers and other stakeholders. The results can help to increase the sustainability of agriculture by reducing external inputs (primarily fungicides) through the promotion of soil biodiversity. Therefore, proper knowledge transfer is aimed to farmers, consultants and decision makers.

Stakeholders consultations

DISCUSSION GROUP

📅 03.11.2020 | Germany (Online).

Identification of farmers' demands for consideration in case studies 10 and 11.

9 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness.

REGIONAL MEETING

📅 19.02.2020 | Germany.

Summarizing feedback of German stakeholders at the WP2 questionnaire; planning the design of case studies 10 and 11.

6 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness.

📅 3.11.2020 | Germany (Online).

Decisions on design of and management in case studies 10 and 11 based on the outcome of the discussion group.

4 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, agribusiness.

📅 19.01.2021 | Germany (Online).

Consultation and discussion of different possibilities to realize the undersowing treatment in case study 10.

8 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, agribusiness.

📅 10.01.2022 | Germany (Online).

FAR informed the Stiftung Rheinische Kulturlandschaft via an online presentation about the SoildiverAgro project and the scientific field experiments in Germany.

23 PARTICIPANTS: Biologists, agronomists and geographers.

📅 03.02.2023 | Germany.

Regional meeting.

6 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users, Scientific community.

Stakeholders consultations

FIELD DAYS

📅 18.10.2021 | Nideggen (Rhineland), Germany.

Oral presentations and an excursion to the experimental plots of Biocontrol of soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi by fungivorous soil fauna communities in potato cropping systems and Plant diversity is tested to promote soil intrinsic self-regulating processes and to enhance fungivorous soil fauna communities in wheat-cropping systems.

38 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, journalists and consultants.

📅 06.06.2023 | Germany.

Field days.

180 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users, scientific community, media.

TRAINING DAYS

📅 19.03.2021 | Germany (Online).

Planning and decision on the technical process to establish the treatments in case study 10.

7 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, agribusiness.

📅 28.10.2021 | Braunschweig, Germany.

Project introduction and presentation of aims and structure as well as first results.

16 PARTICIPANTS: Students.

📅 02.11.2023 | Germany.

Project introduction and presentation of aims and structure as well as first results.

16 PARTICIPANTS: Students, civil society, scientific community.

OTHERS

📅 19/01/2023 | Germany.

Conference of organic farmers.

76 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users, scientific community.

📅 13.02.2023 | Germany.

Biodiversity Seminar.

61 PARTICIPANTS: Direct end users, civil society, scientific community.

CASE STUDY 10 A

Biocontrol of soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi by fungivorous soil fauna communities in conventional wheat cropping systems

OBJECTIVE

The aim of this case study is to identify management practices that promote fungivorous soil fauna communities as antagonists of fungal plant pathogens in conventional wheat production while requiring reduced application rates of fungicides. In this way, input quantities are to be reduced and the natural self-regulating mechanisms of the soil promoted.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

The efficacy of a biostimulant and a plant adjuvant, each in combination with an additive, in strengthening soil self-regulation processes and thus in controlling fungal plant pathogens (*Fusarium*) in conventional wheat cropping systems is assessed.

STATE OF THE ART

In wheat cultivation in the continental region, increasing infestation pressure from soil-borne plant pathogenic fungi such as *Fusarium* poses major challenges for agriculture. *Fusarium* infestation leads to a reduction in yield levels and - due to the formation of mycotoxins - also in yield quality. In particular, factors such as rising temperatures due to global climate change, densely growing stands and tight crop rotations favour the survival and spread of such fungal diseases. In the long term, negative effects on soil health are to be expected, e.g. through the leaching of mycotoxins. In order to reduce the occurrence of fungal diseases, large quantities of external inputs (mainly fungicides) are currently used.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

The case study helps to close knowledge gaps regarding the effects of fungicide reduction on plant parameters and soil biodiversity in conventional wheat cultivation. It provides valuable new insights into the extent to which biostimulants and plant adjuvants are suitable tools to promote natural soil bioregulation and mitigate possible negative effects of fungicide reduction.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

To reduce the incidence of fungal diseases, high levels of external inputs (mainly fungicides) are currently used. These can potentially enter the soil or groundwater or accumulate in the food chain. Moreover, they lead to fungicide resistances in fungal pathogens, so that new pathotypes are constantly emerging that are even more difficult to control. In the long term, a reduction in the use of fungicides and an adaptation of cultivation systems is therefore necessary for sustainable agricultural production.

CROPS

LOCATION

Nideggen (Germany)

PARTNERS

TI

FAR

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Crop rotation, reduced fungicide application, use of biostimulant, use of plant adjuvant

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

8 farmers, 2 of whom use biostimulants, and 10 advisors

→ *Case Study 10 A Infographic (FAR)*

CASE STUDY 10 B

Biocontrol of soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi by fungivorous soil fauna communities in organic potato cropping systems

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this case study is (i) to assess the biocontrol potential of fungivorous soil fauna communities and (ii) to promote fungivorous soil fauna communities in potato cropping systems.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

The potential of strip undersowing (undersowing only in furrows) and broad undersowing (undersowing on ridges and in furrows) to promote fungivorous soil fauna communities and to increase their biocontrol potential in terms of *Fusarium* and *Alternaria* and their mycotoxins in organic potato cultivation is assessed.

STATE OF THE ART

In the continental region, increasing infestation pressure from soil-borne plant pathogenic fungi poses growing challenges to agriculture. This situation leads to the use of more inputs even in organic farming, which affects the resilience of agroecosystems. The external input by organic farmers to combat the problem of fungal pest incidence are low-dose copper-based contact fungicides and high tillage intensity, which reduce functional soil biodiversity. Farmers are advised to consider cultivation breaks of 5 years for potatoes in their crop rotation. For economic reasons, the rotation sequence can be tightened down to 3 years. In the short-term, farmers financially benefit more from comparatively high prizes for potatoes. In the long-term, soil conditions are threatened.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Undersown crops in organic potato cultivation will strengthen soil intrinsic self-regulating processes. A synergistic interaction between farmers' management (top-down control) and soil fauna services (bottom-up control) for fungal plant pest control (i) protects the soil; (ii) increases system resilience in arable land; (iii) reduces management costs and (iv) makes root crop products economically more competitive by improving product quality and avoiding yield depression.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

In the continental region, the risk of infestation with soil-borne fungal plant pathogens such as *Fusarium spec.* and *Alternaria spec.* increases, especially in moist soils, which threatens the quantity and quality of root crops (here: potatoes). This situation leads to higher input use by farmers, which makes the agroecosystem less resilient in the long term and leads to a loss of soil biodiversity.

CROPS

LOCATION

Trippigleben - Klötze (Germany)

PARTNERS

TI

FAR

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Crop rotation, use of undersown crops, use of different undersowing techniques

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

10 farmers, 5 of whom use undersown crops, and 20 advisors

→ Case Study 10 B Infographic (FAR)

CASE STUDY 11

Plant diversity is tested to promote soil intrinsic self-regulating processes and to enhance fungivorous soil fauna communities in wheat-cropping systems

Best Management Practices

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this case study is to assess the potential of plant diversity in wheat cultivation to reduce fungal diseases and strengthen soil intrinsic self-regulating processes. In this context we will investigate (i) wheat grown in extensive farming (reduced seeding rate, no pesticides) as well as (ii) the diversification of the extensive farming of wheat by adding undersown crops (including legumes). Both (i) and (ii) are supposed to increase associated plant diversity within the crop, with (ii) also enhancing sown plant diversity. Both (i) and (ii) are compared to conventionally cropped wheat at the same site.

STATE OF THE ART

Usually a very high level of external inputs (mainly fungicides but also stalk-reducing substances) is used to reduce the incidence of fungal diseases. Increasing amounts of cereals within the crop rotation favour the spread of soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi also in the following vegetation period, leading to even higher fungicide application rates. The reduction of tillage in terms of preventing soil erosion and lowering farmers costs additionally promotes soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

We will identify suitable adjustments of wheat crop rotations that will help farmers to reduce fungal diseases without a further increase of external inputs. In this context the potential of a reduced sowing rate, the avoidance of plant protection products and the cultivation of clover undersowing to promote natural bioregulation in conventional wheat cropping is assessed.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

The promotion of soil intrinsic self-regulating processes and the enhancement of fungivorous soil fauna communities in wheat-cropping systems will help to (i) reduce the amounts of external inputs, mainly fungicides, (ii) enhance the fertility of soil, (iii) improve product quality and (iv) reduce farmers costs and make the grown cereals economically more competitive.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

The cropping of wheat is very susceptible to soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi. Especially in regions of generally high yields due to very fertile soils (e.g. aeolian silt) with tight seed rows, fungal diseases can spread easily, leading to a significant reduction of yield and nutritional quality.

CROPS

LOCATION

Nideggen (Germany)

PARTNERS

TI

FAR

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Crop rotation, reduced sowing rate, no pesticide application, and use of undersown crops

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

10 farmers, 5 of whom use undersown crops, and 20 advisors

→ Case Study 11 Infographic (FAR)

NEMORAL

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER

EULS, (Estonia)

COORDINATION

Merrit Shanskiy

PhD in field crop husbandry, associated professor of soil science at Estonian University of Life Sciences, Chair of Soil Science. Main fields of research are related to soil science and soil biodiversity, plants-soil interactions. EULS researcher-in-charge in the SoildiverAgro project, WP2 leader and involved in several WPs.

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Objective

The agriculture is important and traditional economic activity in Estonia. The sector has long traditions as food and job provider and it is continuously important to Nemoral region. The grain and rape cultivation are the main agricultural crops at local scale. For cultivation, the input by mineral- and organic fertilizers is needed in combination with right soil tillage system. Nowadays, the problem has risen due to the high use of pesticides and monocultures are increasing pest/disease spreading. That is causing the wider use of agrochemicals and different products usage on fields for yield protection, which consequently have impact on soil biology and soil organisms. Soil biological properties are found to be more sensitive toward changes compared to physical and chemical properties, which can be used as an early indication of changes in soil quality and the sustainability of agricultural management practices. Soil is one of the most species-rich, yet one of the most poorly researched habitats of our planet. However, soil organisms have been “out of sight, out of mind” for too long. Several properties or functions of soil fauna can be used to indicate soil quality: the presence of specific organisms and their populations or community analysis (functional groups and biodiversity) and biological processes such as soil structure modification and decomposition rates.

On recent years the weather conditions are very changing, there is rarely two similar years by precipitations and temperatures, which is causing an extra losses in yield, that could be alleviated by the right choice of cultivated crop and agrotechnology. The intensive soil management are replaced nowadays very often by soil sustainable management technologies as minimized tillage or direct sowing. But even with soil sustainable management applications there is still need for pesticide use. Furthermore, no-tillage systems often depend more on the usage of pesticides for plant protection compared to conventional or minimum tillage, which might result in higher number and different combinations of pesticide residues in the soil. However, the combined effects of residue mixtures on soil organisms and the processes they alleviate are unknown. The effect of pesticide residues on non-target soil organisms is not well established due to the diversity of the products and variety of breakdown pathways.

Our case studies are designed to solve the questions about pesticides accumulation rate in the litter layer of no-till cereal fields and on management impact to soil biodiversity with the goal to improve pesticide application and soil biodiversity. Pesticide accumulation in the mulch layer might inhibit their biological degradation, thus could potentially increase their persistence in the soil environment. To reduce the pesticide usage one possibility is to monitor plant health and detect plant diseases before their wider spreading. To solve this problem the control of phytopathogenic fungi by studying the spreading of spores by air in order to improve the pest monitoring and control system.

These are the main challenges for Nemoral agriculture, the results of current project will contribute to the better understanding of soil-plant management systems while transferred to different parties; farmers, producers, policy-makers and land owners. Soil is a living and dynamic entity that requires a unique balance between its physical, chemical and biological components in order to remain productive.

Stakeholders consultations

DISCUSSION GROUP

📅 03.07.2020 | Rapla county, Estonia.

Discussion about field crops performance, soil biodiversity, soil fertility, soil biodiversity management, **project introduction**.

19 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness.

📅 05.12.2022 | Rapla county, Estonia.

Why the soil biodiversity is useful for farmers.

PARTICIPANTS.

REGIONAL MEETING

📅 30.11.2020 | Tartu, Estonia.

Solutions for the cultivation of grains, case study
12 content-pesticides residues in soil, impact to soil biodiversity, phytopathogenic fungi, management of soil biodiversity, searching to find the relationship between soil biological groups, crop production and quality.

26 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers.

FIELD DAYS

📅 3.7.2020 | Rapla county, Estonia.

Organic grain cultivation and related problems solutions. SoilDiverAgro project was introduced to the participants. Active discussion related to crop rotation, soil biology, earthworms was conducted. Overview and final decisions to the questionnaires in Nemoral region.

17 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers.

📅 15-18.07.2022 | Estonia.

Field days.

PARTICIPANTS: Farmers.

TRAINING DAYS

📅 11.03.2020 | Estonia.

Training.

152 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researches, agribusiness, policy makers.

📅 27.03.2022 | Estonia.

Workshop.

PARTICIPANTS.

Stakeholders consultations

OTHERS

📅 11.03.2020 | Tartu, Estonia.

Poster and paper about **earthworms abundance, soil quality** on projects selected farms.

152 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, policymakers agribusiness.

📅 03.12.2021 | Estonia.

Presentation.

PARTICIPANTS.

📅 21.04.2022 | Estonia.

SoildiverAgro workshop to farmers 2022.

PARTICIPANTS.

📅 20.02.2024 | Estonia.

Presentation at the online workshop "Network to Innovate: Soil Biodiversity".

PARTICIPANTS.

📅 18.04.2024 | Estonia.

Maames 2024 expo.

40000 PARTICIPANTS: Innovators, professionals.

📅 28.05.2024 | Estonia.

General Assembly.

PARTICIPANTS: Partners.

📅 05.12.2024 | Estonia.

XV Soil Day.

100 PARTICIPANTS: Leading experts, researchers and practitioners.

📅 16.12.2024 | Estonia.

Information Day focused on agricultural innovation.

PARTICIPANTS.

📅 22-23.01.2025 | Estonia.

Nothern Roots Forum.

450 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, soil health experts, and agronomists.

CASE STUDY 12

Control of phytopathogenic fungi via direct identification and the influence of pesticides use on communities of soil fauna in organic and conventional potatoes cropping systems

Best Management Practices

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this case study is (i) to study the role of airborne inoculum on disease development in relation to climatic conditions (ii) to find out pesticides accumulation rate for no-till fields and impact to soil fauna.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

It is aimed through monitoring system to set up more precise management practices for targeted pesticide application and promote in wider sense the soil fauna in conventional and organic farming. The management practices to be tested in cooperation with farmers including changes in soil management and pesticide application. Burkard 7-day recording volumetric sampler have been used to collect the air-borne fungi present in the air.

STATE OF THE ART

In order to deal with the problem of fungal pest occurrence the higher input of pesticides are used (conventional farming, no-till farming) and high tillage intensity (conventional and organic farming), which reduces functional soil biodiversity. Farmers are advised to follow the crop rotation with cover crops and grains. Following potato, cover crops are sown then cultivated grains are contaminated with mycotoxins. In no-till farming system the soil is covered with a litter layer, that is accumulation point for pesticides from where those are released into soil. For economic reasons, the rotation sequence is 2-3 years. In the long-term, soil conditions are threatened and soil biodiversity lost.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Providing evidence that targeted disease management with reduced input of pesticides should rely on monitoring the phytopathogenic fungi present in the air. The case study also illustrates pesticides behavior on direct sowing fields through the debris layer and influence to the soil fauna and soil quality.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

The measures of current study will help to reduce the external input, through sustainable agricultural management and substantial improvement of soil fauna services for fungal plant pest control. In the results, agroecosystems are more resilient and managed with less monetary costs; while with higher soil biodiversity the yield reductions are avoided and healthier crops are obtained. For targeted IPM implementation the causal agents of the airborne phytopathogenic fungi must be identified fast and accurately. Many phytopathogenic fungi spread long distances through wind dispersal of spores and cause outbreaks far from the source location and also remain viable for several growing seasons.

CROPS

LOCATION

Lääne-Viru County / Põlva County
/ Pärnu County / Saare County /
Viljandi County (Estonia)

PARTNERS

EULS

NGO Soil Innovation Cluster

MTÜ Põllukultuuride klaster

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Crop rotation and crop
diversification

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

10 practitioners and 5 advisors

MONITORING

WINTER WHEAT

POTATO

PESTICIDES ACCUMULATION RATE

Non-inversion tillage

Inverting tillage

Control

MANIPULATING WITH PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS

Airborne spore sampling

IMPACT OF PESTICIDES ACCUMULATION ON SOIL ORGANISMS

FIELD EXPERIMENT

Soil earthworms

Soil microorganisms

Soil nematodes

Soil quality

IMPACT OF PESTICIDES ACCUMULATION ON CROP YIELD AND QUALITY

Crop yield and quality

→ Case Study 12
Infographic (EULS)

BOREAL

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER

Luke, (Finland)

COORDINATION

Doctor (PhD) Krista Peltoniemi is a senior scientist and has expertise on soil microbiomes. She has experience on studies of soil microbial communities (fungi, bacteria, actinobacteria, methanogenic archaea and methanotrophic bacteria), their diversity after environmental changes and their relationships in various environments. Her main task in the projects is to act as a regional coordinator for Boreal region on behalf of all Finnish partners Luke, Petla, Kilpiä and Tyynelä farms. She is involved in all WPs, and her expertise will be utilized in the soil microbiological analyses concerning WP3 and WP5. Deputy coordinator of WP3.

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Objective

Early potato is one of the most important crops grown in the Boreal region. Since it has a very short growing period, there is always a long period of time after the harvest when the soil is left bare without vegetation cover. Therefore, the soil in early potato fields is especially vulnerable to erosion and therefore also loss in carbon and nutrients which in turn are actively recycled or retained by soil organisms. With SoildiverAgro we aim to enhance the biodiversity and functionality of soil micro- and macroorganisms responsible for carbon and nutrient cycles.

Two different approaches are investigated in boreal case studies with early potato to maintain soil biodiversity which in turn enhance soil health and productivity:

- 1) keep the fields covered with cover (or catch) crops,
- 2) use of organic forest-based amendment to prevent carbon and nutrient loss after the early potato harvest.

Traditionally most of the cultivated soils in the Boreal region have been under intensive conventional tillage which often means mouldboard ploughing. Ploughing is used to control weed growth and to aerate soil before sowing, although it also disrupts the natural soil layers and structure. Intensive tillage may result in compaction and degradation of soil causing losses of soil organic matter affecting soil biodiversity and water availability and thus to overall soil health and productivity. In SoildiverAgro we aim to tackle these problems by investigating less intensive tillage management practices combined with direct sowing in the fields of the Boreal region. Case study fields under tillage experiments are focused to finding the best management practices to create a good soil structure that will enhance the environment for soil biodiversity and microbial activity, and thus also better nutrient cycling and their availability for crop plants.

The overall goal of SoildiverArgo is to enhance sustainable agriculture also in the Boreal region, where northern location and long wintertime create extra challenges for farmers.

Stakeholders consultations

DISCUSSION GROUP

📅 05.03.2020 | Finland.

Implementation of possible more sustainable agricultural management practices in Finland.

22 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, agribusiness, policymakers, industry advisors.

📅 19.01.2021 | Finland.

Discussion Group.

20 PARTICIPANTS: Farms and project members involved in WP3.

📅 28.10.2021 | Finland.

Online seminar: “Transition from intensive agriculture into productive and sustainable crop production. How to produce enough food in a sustainable way?”

40 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, students, agribusiness, policymakers, industry advisors.

📅 20.04.2022 | Finland.

National webinar about the diversity and community composition of soil fungi in European wheat fields under organic and conventional farming.

40 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, students, agribusiness, policy makers, industry advisors.

📅 13.09.2023 | Finland.

Regional demonstration workshop at Tyynelä Farm in Finland. Tillage practices and their impact on soil structure and earthworm populations in boreal environments.

20 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, students, agribusiness, policy makers, industry advisors.

📅 04.04.2024 | Finland.

Final workshop and discussion group about the results obtained from all boreal case studies: effects of ploughing, use of catch crops and organic forest-based amendments.

40 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers.

REGIONAL MEETING

📅 25.7.2019 | Finland.

Overview and decisions about the final experimental design of the boreal case studies in Finland.

17 PARTICIPANTS: Boreal region partners (farmers, project members).

📅 20.03.2020 | Finland.

Regional meeting.

17 PARTICIPANTS: Boreal region partners.

📅 07.05.2021 | Finland.

Regional meeting.

17 PARTICIPANTS: Boreal region partners.

📅 21.04.2022 | Finland.

Regional meeting.

17 PARTICIPANTS: Boreal region partners.

📅 08.05.2023 | Finland.

Regional meeting.

17 PARTICIPANTS: Boreal region partners.

Stakeholders consultations

FIELD DAYS

📅 25.7.2019 | Finland.

Cover and companion crops were introduced to participants. Active discussion related to crop rotation, soil structure or protective and companion crops.

75 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers.

📅 21.10.2019 | Finland.

Introduction to winter crops, including case study where winter wheat is directly drilled into the green manure crop.

30 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers.

📅 23.07.2020 | Finland.

Trial establishment and intermediate crops.

240 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers.

📅 24.11.2022 | Finland.

Visit to Kilpiä farm in Finland.

15 PARTICIPANTS: Project members.

TRAINING DAYS

📅 16.08.2022 | Finland.

A field tour, trial presentations and discussions.

40 PARTICIPANTS: stakeholders.

📅 30.08.2024 | Finland.

Training course.

250 PARTICIPANTS: Students.

📅 16.09.2022 | Finland.

About the life of earthworms, and what kind of cultivation methods favour their existence.

20 PARTICIPANTS: Farmers, researchers, advisors.

OTHERS

📅 28.10.2021 | Finland.

External national webinar about “The importance of soil microbiome in sustainable plant protection”.

50 PARTICIPANTS: Researchers, agricultural advisers, vocational agricultural school teachers and students, training and certification providers for the professional users of plant protection products, farmers, pesticide retailers, NGOs.

📅 30.07.2022 | Finland.

Farmari exhibition for Finnish agriculture, forestry and countryside in Mikkeli, Finland.

60000 PARTICIPANTS: Citizens, researchers, stakeholders, farmers.

📅 11.08.2022 | Finland.

Lepaa 2022 Horticultural exhibition.

30 PARTICIPANTS: Researchers, teachers, students, entrepreneurs, experts.

📅 10.01.2024 | Finland.

Finnish Agricultural Science Days.

600 PARTICIPANTS: Researchers, teachers, students, entrepreneurs, experts.

📅 06.01.2025 | Finland.

Soil Science Days 2025.

100 PARTICIPANTS: Researchers, teachers, students, entrepreneurs, experts.

📅 16.01.2025 | Finland.

Scientific Webinar about the effects of farming system on soil microbial diversity and community.

75 PARTICIPANTS: Researchers and students.

📅 18.06.2025 | Finland.

Presentation of the WP5 results and outcomes in the Ecology of Soil Organisms 2025.

250 PARTICIPANTS: Scientist.

CASE STUDY 13

Increase of soil biodiversity through amendment of forest based organic material in potato crops

Best Management Practices

OBJECTIVE

The objective is to test if forest based carbon addition increases soil biodiversity and carbon stocks in the soil.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

We will compare potato harvest, compare microbiome diversity, carbon storage and disease occurrence between treatments in relation to forest based carbon addition.

STATE OF THE ART

Potato cultivation in the boreal area is intensive using deep ploughing, irrigation and mineral fertilization. Eutrophication risk of nearby waters/ground water is high.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Finding adequate forest based material addition is the first step of a new fertilization improving biodiversity and carbon storage of soil.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

Potato cultivation has the risk to loose soil organic carbon due to deep ploughing and irrigation. Addition of forest based organic products adds carbon to soil.

CROPS

LOCATION

Laitila (Finland)

PARTNERS

PETLA

LUKE

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Addition of forest based
amendments

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

13 farmers, 5 of whom are also
advisors

→ Case Study 13 Infographic (PETLA & LUKE)

CASE STUDY 14 A

Contrasting continuous plant cover with inversion tillage in wheat fields

OBJECTIVE

The objective is to experiment and quantify what inversion tillage does to a soil ecosystem, and how it influences plant nutrient uptake and health.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

The test fields have been managed with organic farming with continuous plant cover and minimum tillage. The experimental plots will be ploughed and the control will continue as it has.

STATE OF THE ART

In spite of the drawbacks, organic agriculture relies heavily on mouldboard plough to control weeds. Farmers have misconceptions on its effectivity, some even suggesting that it improves soil health by increasing water infiltration and storage. Some farmers have tested non-inversion tillage in organic farming, but the benefits have not been quantified.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Providing evidence on the damage that inversion tillage does to soil structure, health and biology.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

Organic agriculture relies on mouldboard ploughing for weed control. Inversion tillage and related overwinter fallow is seen to be detrimental to soil organisms and soil health, but the results are not conclusive. The case study will provide results on what happens to soil health when a continuous plant cover crop rotation with shallow tillage is interrupted with mouldboard ploughing.

CROPS

LOCATION

Uusimaa (Finland)

PARTNERS

MTJ

TT

LUKE

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Minimum tillage, and inversion tillage

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

13 farmers, 5 of whom are also advisors

→ Case Study 14 A and 14 B Infographic (MTJ & TT)

CASE STUDY 14 B

Contrasting minimum tillage with inversion tillage in wheat fields

OBJECTIVE

To study differences between minimum tillage and ploughing on soil properties and microbiology on organic farming system.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

The test fields have been managed with organic farming with continuous plant cover and minimum tillage. The experimental plots will be ploughed and the control will continue with developed minimum tillage practices.

STATE OF THE ART

Minimum tillage and direct drilling are not common practices in organic farming but could be utilized with a crimper roller and continuous crop cover.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Minimum tillage is presented as a key method for improving soil biological diversity and functioning.

PROBLEM TO SOLVE

Organic agriculture relies on mouldboard ploughing for weed control. Inversion tillage and related overwinter fallow is seen to be detrimental to soil organisms and soil health, but the results are not conclusive. The case study will provide results on what happens to soil health when a continuous plant cover crop rotation with shallow tillage is interrupted with mouldboard ploughing.

CROPS

LOCATION

South Carelia (Finland)

PARTNERS

MTJ

TT

LUKE

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Minimum tillage, and inversion tillage

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

13 farmers, 5 of whom are also advisors

CASE STUDY 15

Use of catch crop in farmed potatoes fields

OBJECTIVE

The objective is to test how catch crops benefit soil biodiversity and biological soil fertility and related ecosystem functions.

PROPOSED PRACTICES

Catch crops will be sown after the harvest.

STATE OF THE ART

Catch crops benefit soil quality especially after the harvest, as they take up nutrients through the summer and autumn, add carbon to soil, contribute to good soil structure, and promote microbial and faunal function and restrict erosion of soil.

PROGRESS WITH THE CASE STUDY IN RELATION WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Finding out whether catch crops would improve soil structure and quality by decreasing nutrient and carbon loss that hypothetically affect soil biodiversity and biological soil fertility.

PROBLEM TO SOLVED

Growing season for early potato cultivation is short. Thus is expected that practices conducted in fields after harvest would be important for soil community maintaining favorable soil conditions.

CROPS

LOCATION

Laitila (Finland)

PARTNERS

PETLA

LUKE

CROPPING SYSTEMS

Use of catch crops

COMMUNITY OF PRACTITIONERS

13 farmers, 5 of whom are also
advisors

Experimental catch crops plots

Catch crops are sown after early potato harvest to decrease erosion and nutrient leaching from the soil since early potato in the boreal region has a very short growing period and thus soil will be a long time without a proper crop which makes soil susceptible to erosion and carbon and nutrient leaching.

→ Case Study 15
Infographic (PETLA & LUKE)

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STAY TUNED!

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